

On the generation of Markov processes

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In "Suggestions for simulation of set solutions", eqn (13b) is wrong. It should be:

$$C = \exp(-\Delta t/\tau_{att}), \quad D = \sigma_{att} \sqrt{1-C^2} \quad (1a, b).$$

Derivation:

Let $u_{k+1} = Cu_k + Dn_k$, where $n_k \in N(0, 1)$. That is, $E(n_k) = 0$, $E(n_k n_p) = \delta_{kp}$.
Then

$$E(u_{k+1}^2) = E(C^2 u_k^2 + 2CDu_k n_k + D^2 n_k^2) = C^2 E(u_k^2) + D^2 \quad (2)$$

The second equality follows from $E(u_k n_k) = E(u_k)E(n_k) = 0$ (since u_k is independent of n_k) and $E(n_k^2) = 1$. Now if $\{u_k\}$ is a stationary process, we have $E(u_{k+1}^2) = E(u_k^2) = s^2$, where s is the s.d. of the process. Then

$$s^2 = C^2 s^2 + D^2 \quad (3)$$

from which $D^2 = (1-C^2)s^2$; hence (1b) (with $s = \sigma_{att}$).

To derive (1a), compute first

$$E(u_{k+1} u_k) = E(Cu_k^2 + Du_k n_k) = Cs^2. \quad (4)$$

Thus the correlation between u_{k+1} and u_k is $\rho_1 = E(u_{k+1} u_k) / [E(u_k^2)E(u_{k+1}^2)]^{1/2} = Cs^2/s^2 = C$. Then, with $u_{k+2} = Cu_{k+1} + Dn_{k+1}$,

$$E(u_{k+2} u_k) = E(Cu_{k+1} u_k + Du_k n_{k+1}) = CE(u_{k+1} u_k) = C^2 s^2 \quad (5)$$

so that the correlation between u_{k+2} and u_k is $\rho_2 = C^2$. By recursion, $\rho_n = C^n$. Now if the process shall have a correlation length of τ , equal to $\tau/\Delta t$ steps, then the correlation after $\tau/\Delta t$ steps should be $1/e$, i.e.

$$C^{\tau/\Delta t} = e^{-1} \quad (6)$$

yielding (1a).

The erroneous formula in the previous note happened as follows. In practical cases we have $\tau \gg \Delta t$, so that $C^2 = \exp(-2\Delta t/\tau) \simeq 1 - 2\Delta t/\tau$ and $1 - C^2 \simeq 2\Delta t/\tau$. Then (13b) becomes

$$D^2 \simeq 2\sigma_{\text{att}}^2 \Delta t/\tau_{\text{att}}. \quad (7)$$

This was the form originally intended; unfortunately I wrote instead $D = 2\sigma_{\text{att}}^2 \Delta t/\tau_{\text{att}}$. From the dimensions of the two members this is obviously wrong, and at some later time it was therefore "corrected" to

$$D = 2\sigma_{\text{att}} \Delta t/\tau \quad (\text{WRONG!}) \quad (8)$$

which is dimensionally consistent but nevertheless wrong.

The actual standard deviation of the attitude motion generated with the erroneous D (eqn 8) is, according to (3),

$$(\sigma_{\text{att}})_{\text{actual}} = D/(1 - C^2)^{\frac{1}{2}} = \frac{2\Delta t}{\tau_{\text{att}} [1 - \exp(-2\Delta t/\tau_{\text{att}})]^{\frac{1}{2}}} \sigma_{\text{att}} \quad (9)$$

$$\simeq 0.202 \sigma_{\text{att}} \quad (10)$$

for $\Delta t = 2$ and $\tau_{\text{att}} = 100$. Since all simulations so far have been made with these values, the actual attitude s.d. in all simulations has been only 20 % of the intended s.d.! (Because of the initial values of the Markov processes was set to $u_1 = \sigma_{\text{att}} n_0$, the initial s.d. was actually σ_{att} , but decreased with time constant 100 sec finally to settle at $0.2\sigma_{\text{att}}$.)

When correcting this error in the simulation programme, I suggest that the exact expression (1b) is used rather than the approximation (7). It can then be used also with $\tau_{\text{att}} \ll \Delta t$, e.g. if we would like to simulate completely independent attitude errors from one frame to the next. (E.g. $\tau = 0.1$ sec gives correlation $\rho_1 = 2 \cdot 10^{-9}$ between successive frames. $\tau = 0$ would give numerical underflow but is not necessary.)